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TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Description
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
TDR	Trustworthy Digital Repositories
PMB	Project Management Board
SoMe	Social Media
EOSC	European Open-Source Cloud
FAIR Data	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable Data
CD&E Activities	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Activities
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
TTRAM	Transparent Trustworthy Repository Attributes Matrix

Executive Summary

The main goal of FIDELIS is to establish a healthy, vibrant and self-sustaining network of Trustworthy Digital Repositories (TDRs) that will foster a supportive open science environment and guarantee FAIR data sharing also in the future. FIDELIS aims to setup a European network of trustworthy repositories that will support the development and growth of TDRs within the EOSC ecosystem, foster harmonisation and interoperability across repositories to enable an EOSC federation of TDRs, as well as strengthen the upskilling of repositories and expansion of the network through an active training and support programme.

The main goal of the first phase (WP11) of the project's Pillar 5 regarding Strategic alliance, cascading grants, communication and dissemination is to design the overall strategy for dissemination, communication and engagement of the project at all levels, while establishing contacts and introducing collaboration mechanisms to ensure dialogue with the EOSC Partnership and the broad network of data-intensive projects, initiatives and research infrastructures in Europe and beyond. These goals for the first year of the project will be complemented later on with the work to be put in place on behalf of WP12 and WP13 teams (also under the same Pillar 5) for the following years, which will be focused on providing visibility and promotion to the FIDELIS support and training programme and open calls, as well as position the Network as the voice of the trustworthy digital repositories' community and consolidate its role as a key reference in the Open Science landscape in Europe.

The FIDELIS "D11.1 Project communication & dissemination strategy & plan" details a series of objective-oriented target outreach campaigns, an initial stakeholder mapping and Strategic Alliance rolling plan in collaboration with FIDELIS's work on the preparation and establishment of the Network (Pillar 2), harmonisation and guidance efforts (Pillar 3) and engagement with repositories towards consolidation of the Network through training and support (Pillar 4).

All FIDELIS communication and dissemination activities to be performed aim to maximise the communication and dissemination activities of the project during the first period, with the intent to have the same effect during the whole project lifetime and after its conclusion.

The document is divided in specific sections, listing the results achieved during this first reporting period:

- **Section 1 and Section 2** give the overall FIDELIS context within the European Open Science Cloud and FAIR-enabling landscapes. It also refers to the collaboration with EOSC-EDEN project;
- **Section 3** describes the FIDELIS stakeholders and purpose of engagement;
- **Section 4** provides an overview of FIDELIS communication campaigns and goals, which are detailed in:
 - **Section 4.1:** focused on Campaign #1: FIDELIS project communication;
 - **Section 4.2:** focused on Campaign #2: TDR Network expansion;
 - **Section 4.3:** focused on Campaign #3: TDR Network promotion and visibility;
 - **Section 4.4:** focused on Campaign #4: Strategic Alliances.

- **Section 5:** outlines FIDELIS presence at third-party events, as well events organised by the project, along with other initiatives;
- **Section 6:** provides an overview of how FIDELIS will monitor the achievement of its communication and dissemination KPIs;
- **Section 7:** draws some overall conclusions and reinforces the mindset that the success of FIDELIS communication and dissemination will rely on collaboration of all FIDELIS partners

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1 Introduction

The FIDELIS project will establish and consolidate a European network of FAIR-enabling trustworthy digital repositories that will unite the repository community and offer them a common voice to better interact with research communities, technology providers, policy makers and funders, and respond in a more coordinated and impactful manner to the needs of European researchers. The FIDELIS network will be the main output of the FIDELIS project. During the project lifetime, the consortium will co-create together with the repository community an appropriate business and governance model for the FIDELIS network, start the operations, grow the membership base and craft a sustainability plan with the objective that the FIDELIS network will reach the necessary organisational maturity to live on after the project finishes in December 2027.

The European digital repository landscape is very varied, and there is no standard definition of what makes a digital repository “trustworthy”. While the project is building the FIDELIS network (announcement in April 2025¹) launched in and defining its value proposition and modus operandi, it is also working with the repository community to deliver a community-endorsed definition of what constitutes a trustworthy digital repository (TDR) in the context of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). This will be achieved by compiling an overall matrix of characteristics, functions and activities exhibited across a broad range of repositories – the Transparent Trustworthy Repository Attributes Matrix – TTRAM, also called as the FIDELIS Matrix, that will harmonise, inform and validate existing criteria and guide repositories in achieving a TDR status, reflecting the highest standards of trustworthiness.

In addition to compiling a harmonised matrix of repository capabilities and characteristics, the project aims to enhance interoperability across repositories and enable their EOSC federation. It will help repositories to semantically describe themselves in a uniform, machine-readable manner and provide a set of recommendations, best practices, and solutions (e.g. APIs and standards) that will increase the discoverability of repositories’ capabilities and services making a federated search across multiple repositories possible. TDRs play a key role in research ecosystems, providing secure and sustained access to digital research objects over the long-term. Thus, they are also integral for achieving a sustainable EOSC and preserving Europe’s research data assets for future generations in a findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable form. The FIDELIS project will explore ways to bring TDRs to the emerging EOSC Federation and support their technical federation.

As a Coordination and Support Action (CSA), the FIDELIS project has a strong emphasis on stakeholder engagement and community building. It aims to improve repositories’ FAIR-enabling capabilities and trustworthiness, helping them to become recognised as authoritative sources of high-quality data. FIDELIS training and support programme will strengthen the upskilling of repositories in Europe,

¹ <https://eden-fidelis.eu/news/fidelis-network-trustworthy-digital-repositories-has-officially-launched>

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enable peer-to-peer support and foster their integration into the FIDELIS network to ensure that repositories also remain trustworthy and FAIR-enabling over time.

FIDELIS Work Package (WP) 11 is tasked to design the overall strategy for dissemination, communication and stakeholder engagement, while establishing contacts and introducing collaboration mechanisms to ensure dialogue with the EOSC Partnership and other strategic initiatives to position FIDELIS network as part of the European Open Science landscape. WP11 will support other WPs in engaging repositories, data-intensive projects, initiatives, and other stakeholders in Europe and beyond and deliver an impactful communication and dissemination scheme to support the FIDELIS project and the emerging FIDELIS network to meet their objectives.

Due to the lump sum grant and year-long WPs (except for WP1), the work of WP11 will be continued and complemented by the efforts of WP12 in 2026 and WP13 in 2027 (see figure below). In order not to confuse the reader with WP numbering, we will refer in this document to the names of the pillars i.e. the cross-cutting thematic areas around which the project activities are organised.

Figure 1 FIDELIS workplan

2 How FIDELIS Communication, Dissemination and stakeholder engagement is organised

FIDELIS pillar 5 Communication and Outreach is composed of three consecutive one-year-long WPs that are tasked to implement the communication, dissemination and engagement (DC&E) strategy and plan as defined in this document, supporting the other pillars to maximise the impact of their activities. All pillar 5 WPs are led by Trust-IT with participants from CSC - IT Center for Science, KNAW-DANS, CESSDA ERIC and COMMpla, and are structured around the same core tasks throughout the project lifetime:

- Strategic Alliance (including stakeholder engagement) led by CSC

- Communication, Dissemination & TDR Forum led by Trust-IT
- Cascading grants platform set-up, management and administration led by COMMpla

Pillar 5 convenes in monthly meetings to coordinate the work across the tasks and steer the overall effort of pillar 5. Trust-IT as the leading organisation of the pillar is part of the FIDELIS Project Management Board (PMB), the supervisory governance body composed of all pillar leaders, where the discussions about the implementation of the overall project strategy and work plan are held, including specifically communication and outreach needs and activities.

Since its start FIDELIS has established a close collaboration with its “sister project” EOSC EDEN that has been awarded via the same funding call². Both projects run from 1 January 2025 to 31 December 2027 with complementary objectives. While FIDELIS concentrates on consolidating the position of FAIR-enabling trustworthy digital repositories in Europe and upskilling the key actors in the area, EOSC EDEN aims to enhance digital preservation strategies at national and European level, providing new solutions and approaches that help institutions select and preserve high-quality FAIR research outputs long-term.

The collaboration between EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS started at the joint kick-off meeting on 4-6 February 2025 in Helsinki, Finland. Different collaboration mechanisms were established to ensure alignment, maximisation of the efforts and outcomes as well as to avoid overlaps and duplication of activities. The cross-project collaboration is monitored by the **joint PMB of EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS** which gathers all WP leaders and their deputies as well as the project coordinators from both projects, to oversee that content synchronization is well organised and discuss any further alignment needs or potential synergies.

Due to the many similarities in the target audiences, the projects joined forces and established a **joint communication and dissemination working group** where the EOSC EDEN communication team is represented by CSC (leading EOSC EDEN T4.4), OPFNL and KU Leuven, while the FIDELIS team is represented by Trust-IT and CSC, with the additional support of KNAW-DANS and CESSDA ERIC for the work on Strategic alliance tasks. The group meets online on a fortnight’s basis to coordinate editorial work, communication activities and joint engagement of stakeholders. A shared workspace is set-up for a smooth collaboration.

In the framework of the joint communication and dissemination EOSC EDEN - FIDELIS working group, **a shared editorial plan** was created and will be maintained, to plan writing and publication of content pieces across the EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS channels (website, SoMe, newsletter, and content for media dissemination), as further explained in the sections below. Costs for licences and third-party tools to be used will also be shared between the two projects, to ensure there is no double accounting and maximisation of financial resources available in the two consortia. The projects agreed on designing, developing and running **one unique website**³ as the single entry point for public access to information

²<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-search;callCode=HORIZON-INFRA-2024-EOSC-01>

³ <https://eden-fidelis.eu/>

about the two projects, with a **shared privacy policy** for collecting and sharing users' data between the identified data processors from the two consortia. The two projects agreed to maintain **two different communities on Zenodo**, to ensure proper acknowledgement and copyright of the documents and deliverables to be produced, as well as social media channels which will be different, each project maintaining its own channel. **A joint newsletter service** will be used to disseminate news alerts from both projects to the **FIDELIS community (composed by members brought on board from both FIDELIS and EOSC EDEN projects)**, which will be unique, gathering users from website registrations (to events, surveys, open calls) as well as from surveys that might run outside the website and for which proper consent will be asked to the respondents.

Where feasible and according to FIDELIS and EOSC EDEN privacy agreements and DMPs⁴, both projects will also exploit synergies in stakeholder engagement activities and share survey findings with each other not to have to collect the same information from the stakeholders twice. A stakeholder database is being developed by the EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS stakeholder engagement teams to have an overview of each other's target stakeholder groups, priorities and expected impact.

3 FIDELIS Stakeholder Engagement

This chapter presents the target stakeholder groups and strategies to engage them in the FIDELIS project activities and the emerging FIDELIS network of trustworthy digital repositories.

3.1 Stakeholder Engagement Objectives

FIDELIS stakeholder engagement objectives are tied to the main objectives of the project to i) establish, operate and consolidate a vibrant, self-sustaining European network of FAIR-enabling trustworthy digital repositories, ii) foster the harmonisation of the definition of trustworthy repositories and facilitate the technical federation of repositories across EOSC and iii) enhance repositories' FAIR- enabling capabilities and support them in adopting best practices, tools, and services to achieve trustworthiness.

Therefore, the FIDELIS stakeholder engagement strategy builds on three underlying elements:

- i) Co-creation approach to building the FIDELIS network to ensure that it provides added value to its current and future members
- ii) Transparent and inclusive methodology to produce a stable and community-endorsed definition of TDRs in the EOSC ecosystem
- iii) Providing a framework for repositories to support each other in becoming and remaining trustworthy over time

⁴ A data sharing agreement is currently being drafted by the CSC legal department, to be signed by data controllers and data processors from both projects.

A stakeholder database⁵ is being populated with the list of players both FIDELIS and EOSC Eden will engage with during the projects' timeframe.

3.2 Target Stakeholder Groups

The FIDELIS network can leverage on a powerful legacy from its project consortium. **Six scientific communities** are project partners: CESSDA (Social Sciences), CLARIN (Linguistics), ELIXIR (Biomedical Sciences), INRAE (Agri-food), ESRF (Physical Sciences) and DKRZ (Climate Science). FIDELIS partners' networks include over **200 active digital repositories**, and the consortium has already identified **36 early adopters** and the provisional and future members of the network (see Annex 1).

On top of this, the FIDELIS project identified 8 key stakeholder groups to maximise outreach. Each of the groups (listed below) is part of Europe's research data ecosystem and have a specific role. For this reason, an engagement plan for each group is provided. While the key messages may vary per target group, the overall purpose of the messaging is to provide a coherent story on why trustworthy data archives are critical for EOSC, Open Science and long-term data sustainability. Following the campaign-based approach, the different stakeholders will be reached via a combination of channels and activities described in the figure below.

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Figure 2 FIDELIS stakeholders

The stakeholder database being developed by the EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS stakeholder engagement teams goes deeper in the analysis by mapping the above categories in the following sub-categories: *Community based organization; Community based initiative; Digital Europe Programme, Discipline-specific communities; EOSC ecosystem Horizon Europe project; Open Science and FAIR Initiatives; Research Infrastructure; Research performing organisation; University; Repository; Service provider; Library; Archive; Museum; LAM (Library, Archive, Museum); Digital (LTDP) archive; Funder; Policy maker.*

The identified stakeholder groups are all the target recipients of specific campaigns and related activities, as listed in Chapter 4 below. In the following paragraphs the stakeholder categories are further detailed and information on the related campaigns are also provided.

3.2.1 SG1 European Digital Repositories

European Digital Repositories are a critical element in the research ecosystem, providing a key infrastructural component in the research data lifecycle. They provide secure and sustained access to digital research objects, enabling researchers to both share research outputs with their communities

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and the public, as well as access, potentially reuse and refer to the outputs of other researchers. According to the re3data registry, there are almost 300 digital repositories within the European Union.⁶ Together they share a rich history. They are highly diverse in terms of their research culture, the disciplines they represent and the countries they reside in.

The first actions undertaken with digital repositories were both taken place in April 2025, with the launch of the FIDELIS network, as well as the landscape survey where repositories shared their current needs in specific areas (collecting 159 responses in total). A call for repositories to join the network as preliminary members was distributed to an initial list of 37 repositories and promoted across social media channels and partners' networks, promoting the Core activities that the Network will engage in, namely:

- **Stakeholder advocacy and engagement.** The FIDELIS Network aims to grow into an advocacy group for FAIR-enabling trustworthy digital repositories.
- **Networking and facilitation of knowledge exchange,** e.g. on common legal topics specific for Trustworthy Digital Repositories, such as GDPR and IPR aspects.
- **Coordination and development.** The FIDELIS Network will support members to implement trustworthy and FAIR-enabling (best) practices, policies, standards and tools; foster standardisation and interoperability across repositories to enable an EOSC federation of TDRs; provide training and support for TDRs and TDR staff.

The benefits that provisional members will have by being part of the Network will be:

- Contribute to designing the Network, its governance and sustainability.
- Engage in the pilot support offer in the first year. This offer will consist of various solutions – services, tools, methodologies, and policies – being provided by project partners and EOSC projects. Member repositories will test solutions in their own local environment, supported by FIDELIS project partners. The feedback from participating Network members will in turn influence the support offer in the next project years. The Network members will be among the first to hear about FIDELIS cascading grants for later support actions.
- Benefit from engaging with the other Network members, hearing about future projects and relevant EOSC developments, and potentially meeting future project partners.

Furthermore, this stakeholder group will be the main target for the training and support programmes to be delivered by FIDELIS. The project communication and dissemination team will support the execution of these programmes, which will be tailored to different specific needs from repositories.

Related communication campaigns:

- #2 TDR Network expansion
- #3 TDR Network promotion and visibility

3.2.2 SG2: Research Infrastructures

⁶ <https://www.re3data.org/search?query=&countries%5B%5D=EEC>

In general research infrastructures' national, European or intergovernmental facilities provide resources and services for research communities to conduct research and foster innovation. They can be used beyond research e.g., for education or public services, and they may be single-sited, distributed, or virtual.

ERICs are RI of European importance on a non-economic basis and to promote innovation and knowledge and technology transfer in ERA. Many repositories are part of RIs. The FIDELIS consortium itself counts specific ERICs for a stronger and impactful engagement with these communities from different domains (e.g. CESSDA from social sciences, ELIXIR from life sciences, INRAE for agriculture, food and the environment, DKRZ from climate and earth system research, CLARIN from languages and humanities, amongst others).

RIs are important to FIDELIS as they are a key service provider to research. They are responsible for high-quality research and archive data. RIs, therefore, especially in an international setting can be facilitators and multipliers of best data archiving practices in their communities. The FIDELIS project and network can provide RIs with knowledge exchange opportunities to support sharing of best practices with other communities.

3.2.3 G3 Certification authorities

Certification provides an external validation that repositories which claim to preserve and provide access to digital resources both now and in the future are up to the challenge. Certification will make repositories' stakeholders more confident that the data they contain will be protected, properly managed, and available for future reuse. But, more importantly, going through a certification process will help repositories to further professionalize their organisational structure, workflows, services, etc. Currently, the main certification standards are CoreTrustSeal, nestor and ISO16363.⁷

The FIDELIS project will create an overall matrix of characteristics, functions and activities exhibited across a broad range of repositories, the Transparent Trustworthy Repository Attributes Matrix (TTRAM). This matrix will inform an in-depth examination of the information artefacts that support repository practices and provide evidence for assessment/certification. The matrix will harmonise, inform and validate existing assessment/certification criteria rather than replace them, and to support and guide repositories in achieving a TDR status.

Next to this, FIDELIS will also develop and provide a framework for organising repositories to support each other in becoming and remaining trustworthy.

In short, the FIDELIS project will support repositories to further professionalise and become more trustworthy and FAIRER enabling. This focus aligns with the remit of the certification authorities. Participating in the support and engagement activities of the project and joining the FIDELIS Network will help repositories mature and get ready for certification as a TDR.

⁷ <https://www.coretrustseal.org>

The FIDELIS project can act as a facilitator between certification authorities (e.g., such as CoreTrustSeal) and new or not yet matured repositories. New stakeholders or beneficiaries from the pilots could in the future become CoreTrustSeal certified.

Through FIDELIS and members of ERICs involved in FIDELIS (e.g. CESSDA, CLARIN and ELIXIR) other nodes can benefit from the acquired knowledge.

Related communication campaigns:

- #2 TDR Network expansion
- #3 TDR Network promotion and visibility

3.2.4 SG4: Funding Agencies

Funding agencies in the context of the FIDELIS project refer to bodies funding trustworthy repositories on both European and national levels. These include the European Commission and other national funding agencies.

FIDELIS’ value proposition to funding agencies is to pinpoint and understand the common challenges faced by the funding agencies’ community and to include those challenges in the policy and funding agendas that the project aims to create. By doing so, FIDELIS can provide a set of recommendations, best practices and solutions in terms of trustworthy repositories to funding agencies so that the shared guidelines serve the funding agencies’ best interest. The guidelines will be especially useful in the future in grants and funding mechanisms, ensuring that EOSC and EU money is well invested. When liaising with funding agencies, FIDELIS will also raise their awareness on what is required from their side to build up trustworthy repositories.

To build a set of guidelines for funding agencies, FIDELIS will include them in its outreach campaigns to facilitate dialogue and learn about the current challenges. Engagement efforts will be beneficial to both parties: FIDELIS will be able to influence its network from the funding agencies’ perspective, and the funding agencies, in turn, will benefit from the shared guidelines in the long-term.

Related communication campaigns:

- #3 TDR Network promotion and visibility

3.2.5 SG5: Service providers and suppliers of data repository technology

Service providers and suppliers of data repository technologies (e.g. ARKIVUM, Google, GMV Soluciones Globales Internet, PiqlAS, SafeSpring, LIBNOVA, Giaretta Associates) are relevant mainly for FIDELIS Pillar 3 working on the harmonisation of TDRs and their interoperability. FIDELIS will engage this target stakeholder group via the collaboration with EOSC EDEN project to gather and consolidate technical requirements for curation and preservation services needed by repositories.

Related communication campaigns:

- #3 TDR Network promotion and visibility

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3.2.6 SG6: Policymakers

Policymakers include national and EU-level actors responsible for shaping policies around research infrastructures, open science, and data governance, such as national parliaments and ministries, research councils, and the European Commission and Parliament, as well provide funds to specific topics relevant to the European overall landscape. They are key to ensuring alignment of open science long-term data preservation strategies with broader policy agendas (e.g. European Research Area Policy Agenda) and funding priorities.

FIDELIS is significant because it supports the EU’s strategic goals related to open science and data accessibility. TDRs ensure that the research data remains Findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. By establishing a European network of TDRs supports the EOSC vision to provide European researchers, innovators, companies, and citizens with a federated and open multi-disciplinary environment where they can publish, find and reuse data, tools and services for research, innovation and educational purposes and at large it contributes to a more coordinated and interoperable data landscape.

Key messages

- TDRs are essential enablers of Open Science, ensuring long-term access to publicly funded research.
- By establishing TDRs, the project supports the enhancement of data sharing and collaboration across Europe.
- FIDELIS project is aligned with EU priorities of supporting FAIR Data and Open Science.

Policymakers can be invited to join seminars later in the project to learn more about the outcomes of FIDELIS and why they matter. These sessions are a great chance to show the real value of the project and how its results can support smarter policies around research data and long-term preservation.

Related communication campaigns:

- #3 TDR Network promotion and visibility

3.2.7 SG8: EOSC-related actors

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is an ambitious European initiative that aims to create a Web of FAIR data and services for science in Europe. It will offer a federated virtual environment where researchers can find, share, store, process, analyse and reuse FAIR research outputs across borders and scientific disciplines. The implementation of EOSC is a long-term process involving many actors, but the end goal is to create a European Knowledge Commons to harness Europe’s untapped digital potential through a unified, accessible infrastructure for high-quality research outputs and support the Open Science movement. EOSC is also very much linked to Europe’s competitiveness and digital sovereignty.

EOSC Tripartite Governance

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The EOSC Tripartite Governance is a concept of strategic coordination between the European Commission (representing the European Union), the EOSC Association (representing the European research community) and the EOSC Steering Board (representing the EU Member States and Associated Countries to Horizon Europe Framework Programme) to resource and support the implementation of the EOSC.

The appointed representatives of the three parties of the EOSC Tripartite Governance form the Tripartite Group, which is tasked to prepare commonly agreed positions and support the strategic steering of the EOSC Tripartite Governance in what concerns the establishment and operation of EOSC, including the EOSC Federation.

EOSC Nodes and resource providers

The EOSC Federation will consist of multiple EOSC Nodes that are interconnected and can collaborate to share and manage FAIR research output across scientific disciplines and geographical borders according to the vision depicted in the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) of EOSC. The EOSC Nodes will be entry points for users to the EOSC Federation, with each node offering its own and possibly third-party services, including data reposing and accessing services.

At the time of writing this deliverable, the build-up phase of the EOSC Federation has just begun with the 14 candidate EOSC nodes that were selected for the first wave of deployment of the Federation, and the first edition of the EOSC Federation Handbook, explaining the organisational and technical characteristics of the Federation, has been just released.

The Tripartite Group has a central role in supporting the coordination and steering of the processes of establishing the EOSC Federation. Simultaneously, discussions about the future governance model for EOSC in the post-2027 era when the new Framework Program (FP10) starts and the current co-programmed European Partnership under the Horizon Europe Framework Program finishes, are ongoing.

The FIDELIS network can contribute to the EOSC Federation by provisioning resources such as datasets, publications, research outputs etc. The network itself will not operate any federation services but will rely on EOSC Federation Services (registries and brokering), and potentially on any enhancements to this infrastructure developed by EOSC EDEN project. Two important extensions to the EOSC Federation infrastructure are expected from the EDEN project and will be promoted by FIDELIS:

- 1) a registry of services and repositories, with attributes reflecting a variety of compliance states in respect of formal and extended criteria for trustworthiness (defined in collaboration with FIDELIS),
- 2) a service that will guide end users, especially depositors, towards the most appropriate service for their needs.

The FIDELIS project and the emerging Network will have to closely follow how the EOSC Federation unfolds and take notice of any updates in terms of the operational structure of the Federation and interoperability requirements.

The objective is to explore ways to facilitate the sharing and implementation of federated repository services in the EOSC Federation and enhance the interoperability across TDRs regardless of the node through which they will be accessible to the end users.

Value propositions / key messages of FIDELIS towards EOSC & EOSC Federation:

- FIDELIS Network provides a list of TDRs, the repositories with the highest levels trustworthiness providing high-quality, FAIR research outputs
- Standards, APIs, and best practices that enable technical federation of TDRs in the EOSC

EOSC Projects

Several projects funded through Horizon Europe are contributing to the development and deployment of the European Open Science Cloud. The FIDELIS project has identified the following projects as relevant for its activities and will analyse the importance of new projects that will be funded in the future.

Table 1 Relevant EOSC projects identified

Project	Why relevant for FIDELIS? (e.g. outputs to utilise)
EOSC EDEN	EOSC EDEN is directly related to FIDELIS as it develops the frameworks, tools, and expert network for sustainable digital preservation and curation. Furthermore, it explicitly aims to connect with and support the long-term sustainability of the Trustworthy Digital Repository Network that FIDELIS is building.
FAIR-IMPACT	Through its practical outputs on PIDs, FAIR assessments, and certification, FAIR-IMPACT strengthens the foundations upon which FIDELIS builds its trusted repository network. Ten FIDELIS partners are also members and data processors of the FAIR-IMPACT project, which counts 3100+ registered individuals from 91 countries, representing 850+ Research Performing Organisations, 430+ Repositories and Data service providers, and 37 National Initiatives. All of them will be invited to join the FIDELIS community.
FAIRCORE4EOSC	The nine technical components developed in FAIRCORE4EOSC, like the Metadata Schema & Crosswalk Registry, provide tools and services that FIDELIS may utilize to improve discoverability of repositories’ capabilities and services, interoperability, and EOSC integration of TDRs.
Skills4EOSC	By connecting competence centers and offering common training methodologies, Skills4EOSC feeds into FIDELIS’s training pillar and supports upskilling across its repository network.

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EOSC Data Commons	EOSC Data Commons is relevant for FIDELIS as it supports improved data lifecycle management, including preservation, aligning with FIDELIS’s goal of enabling long-term, trustworthy access to FAIR data.
SciLake	SciLake is important for FIDELIS because it develops tools for creating and managing Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs), which can enhance the discoverability and interoperability of data within Trustworthy Digital Repositories. By integrating these SKGs, FIDELIS can improve its repositories' ability to connect research outputs, making data more accessible and reusable across various scientific domains.
OSCARS	<p>The OSCARS project fosters the uptake of Open Science in Europe through the Science Clusters, representing a wide range of publicly-funded Research Infrastructures (RIs) in Europe. OSCARS will establish Clusters’ Open Science Competence Centres and organises training activities that can potentially be relevant for co-location and disciplinary/cross-disciplinary collaboration.</p> <p>It brings together five major science clusters: ENVRI-FAIR (environmental sciences), EOSC-Life (life sciences), ESCAPE (astronomy and particle physics), PaNOSC (neutron and light source sciences), and SSHOC (social sciences and humanities), to build lasting open science services and practices. These clusters represent a wide range of research communities with strong needs for high-quality, trustworthy data infrastructures. Many of their repositories can be candidates for FIDELIS certification, and their experience can help test and refine our approaches across disciplines.</p>
EOSC United	By supporting the European Commission and EOSC EU Node contractors in promoting resource uptake and uniting the research community within the EOSC federation, EOSC United could provide a possibility for disseminating the resources provided by TDRs once their technical federation has been solved and the resources are available via the Federation.
EOSC Gravity	EOSC GRAVITY is relevant for FIDELIS as the new CSA continuing the work of the EOSC Focus project in supporting the EOSC partnership in further consolidating and coordinating the EOSC ecosystem. FIDELIS will participate in EOSC coordination activities and be an active member of the EOSC community.

Related communication campaigns:

- #3 TDR Network promotion and visibility
- #4 Strategic Alliance

3.2.8 SG7: Individuals

European researchers are also considered a target audience as individuals. They will benefit from FIDELIS contribution to consolidate open science practices, easy identification of the repositories to

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refer to in their research activities, easier way to access and share data across repositories thanks to shared and standardised data management practices that FIDELIS will boost.

3.3 Stakeholder Engagement Strategy & Plan

The FIDELIS stakeholder engagement strategy follows the progress of the project activities and is strongly linked to communication and dissemination to ensure that the right stakeholders are aware of the opportunities to provide input and participate at the right time. The stakeholder engagement strategy presented in this chapter is implemented with the help of a living work plan that is maintained in the project wiki and can be easily updated and populated with logistical information.

Co-create FIDELIS Network

Currently, at the European level there are only few European data archives that are organised in networks and consortia. Among those and project partner of FIDELIS are the “Network beacons” CESSDA ERIC for the Social Sciences, CLARIN ERIC for Linguistics, ELIXIR for Biomedical Sciences, INRAE in the Agri-food domain, ESRF for Physical Sciences and DKRZ for Climate Science. Together with other FIDELIS partners, the network includes over 200 active digital repositories. The project will leverage the network during the project: Each partner has identified a few repositories within their immediate area that are interested to engage with the Network in a first phase (see the list of “early adopters” in the annex). In a second phase other repositories will be onboarded in the TDR Network members such as repositories hosted by university libraries (not visible in the above graph) or Open Repositories (IMPACT-REPO). Specific training action plans⁸ for staff of those repositories such as repository managers and technical staff will be developed.

The work on co-creating a sustainable business-model and value-add for the FIDELIS network will begin by inserting questions in the FIDELIS landscape survey, a project-wide stakeholder engagement effort early in the first project year to collect important information from repositories in Europe and beyond to guide project activities across pillars 2, 3 and 4.

During the first project year, Pillar 2 will process the input received from the FIDELIS Landscaping survey together with the “**Network beacons**” i.e. the repositories part of the project consortium. Supported by Pillar 5, Pillar 2 will organise public information sharing sessions and consultation workshops to present the early versions of the business-model and test the proposed value-add with the repository community.

Another major stakeholder engagement effort in year 1 will be the onboarding of the **early adopters** i.e. the repositories within the immediate reach of the project consortium partners to the FIDELIS Network, which was officially launched in April 2025. The project will capture the experiences of the early adopters in compelling TDR success stories to disseminate the Network to potential new members.

⁸ <https://libereurope.eu/article/action-plan-for-open-repositories-in-europe-impact-repo/>

During the second project year, the focus of stakeholder engagement activities will be on growing the Network membership base via campaign 2 and achieving consensus with the Network members and the wider European TDR community on a sustainability plan for the Network, covering governance, resourcing, financing, and value-add to members. Further public information sharing sessions and workshops are envisioned to this end.

The FIDELIS Network will also need to engage in discussions with the key actors in the EOSC landscape to find out how to best position the FIDELIS Network and its member repositories to EOSC in a sustainable manner.

The third and final project year is characterised by the transition of the FIDELIS network to the post-project era and ensuring sufficient resources to continue the Network’s operations. Growing the Network membership base via campaign 2 will continue and dissemination efforts will gear up for increased recognition of FIDELIS Network’s definition of trustworthiness and the list of EOSC TDRs.

TDR harmonization and interoperability

In parallel with the co-creation of the FIDELIS Network, the project aims to engage repositories and other stakeholders in an interactive process to reach a consensus of what constitutes a trustworthy repository in the context of EOSC and enable their EOSC federation.

The objectives and initial drafts of the TTRAM matrix will be presented in public webinars early in the project lifetime. Repositories and service providers and suppliers of data repository technology will be invited to provide their feedback on them. The first consolidated version of the matrix is expected in autumn 2025. Further refinements will follow in interactive TTRAM workshops that will be organised online or in conjunction with relevant events during the second and third project years.

Questions in the FIDELIS landscape survey early in 2025 will provide the first impetus for preparing the EOSC federation of TDRs. The survey results will help the project in compiling a topical overview of technical and organisational repository standards, recommendations, existing modes of federation, best practices and solutions for accessing, processing, storing, preserving and disseminating digital objects, and tools, classifications, semantic standards, catalogues or registries that are used to manage and access digital objects, as well as understand repositories expectations towards the FIDELIS Network.

Based on the survey data and community feedback on TTRAM, the project will form a tiered approach to describe what would be expected from a repository to be at a certain level of capability and maturity. Feedback and input will be collected through webinars and the cascading grant programme, in collaboration with Pillar 4 (training).

Technical repository service providers will be engaged through the collaboration with EOSC EDEN to consolidate requirements for repository federation & interoperability. Ultimately, this collaborative effort will compel service providers to develop service catalogues that are more comparable, supporting more cost-effective evaluation, procurement and cumulative negotiation for trustworthy repositories within EOSC.

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During the last project year, the project will illustrate, through use cases, how repositories align with the harmonised TTRAM matrix of repository capabilities and characteristics. There will be a feedback loop to iteratively grow and improve the matrix as repositories deploy it in real life. The project will also provide guidelines and explore the tools used within the Network to increase a harmonised use of semantic artefacts. Semantic artefact catalogues providers (such as the OntoPortal Alliance and the EBI Ontology Lookup Service and its reuses), other metadata standard related initiatives and specific vocabulary services (e.g. SSHOC, CESSDA) will be engaged to promote the use of semantic artefacts within each TDR of the Network.

4 FIDELIS Communication Campaigns

FIDELIS will implement a 36-month CD&E Strategy structured around four major campaigns, facilitating an agile implementation and assessment of activities across key target audiences.

The CD&E Strategy will:

- **Promote the project and its results to all stakeholders:** Trust-IT will lead project branding and communications, including website construction and content updates, storytelling and social media outreach, working with all Partners and their associated networks to ensure high visibility for the project and its results. This will be implemented via a specific project communication campaign **“Campaign #1: FIDELIS project communication,”** highlighting the project’s impact on the identified target communities.
- **Maximise engagement of key target audiences** throughout the project and beyond: Pillar 5 partners, in collaboration with WP and Task leaders, will roll out four targeted communication campaigns, each serving a specific purpose, supporting key project activities and maximising exploitation of project outputs for lasting impact beyond the project: **“Campaign #2: TDR Network expansion,” “Campaign #3 TDR Network promotion and visibility,”** and **“Campaign #4 “Strategic alliances.”**

While interlinked, these campaigns utilise a variety of actions, tailored to specific stakeholder groups. This way, we ensure a consistent and efficient engagement in achieving the FIDELIS project objectives, such as the set up and operability of TDRs network within the EOSC ecosystem, fostering TDR’s interoperability and harmonisation efforts, and upskilling of repositories and Network expansion beyond project duration.

4.1 Campaign #1: FIDELIS project communication

The purpose of Campaign 1 is to ensure the project, its assets and results are communicated via its official channels with a consistent identity. The campaign targets all stakeholders via the activities described below.

4.1.1 Branding

The project branding was re-designed from the proposal phase, for FIDELIS to align with existing EOSC brand identity. The project’s visual identity aims at ensuring a distinctive look and feel across the entire

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set of FIDELIS communication tools. The combination of project’s blue and yellow with EOSC - approved font connects the project with other EOSC-related projects, while maintaining a unique brand identity. The agreed upon institutional font is Roboto, in its regular and bold use. The colour palette that should be used across the communication materials includes Yellow HEX: #FBB03B, Blue HEX: #001B6D and Black HEX: #040405. The various shades of blue were previously utilised by EOSC projects supporting TDRs, so the choice of blue for FIDELIS represents the continuation of such efforts.

The branding and FIDELIS logo are to be used in all project dissemination and communication tools. In addition to the logo, promotional material has been developed for initial outreach and will be further evolved during the project for all partners to use. Currently, partners can use roll-up banners, flyers, and templates, either in digital or printed formats, available in the shared Confluence FIDELIS space, for further promotion of FIDELIS. A variety of materials will be developed based on a needs assessment during the project lifetime, and will be used to raise awareness, and provide tailored messaging for different target audiences, using call-to-actions. All communication materials will be available in the project’s internal repositories for the benefit of the consortium, while public materials will be accessible via the public website.

Table 2 KPIs related to project branding

Activity	KPI by M36
Project branding package with logos, templates, and collaterals available	1 kit
Roll-up banners (layout), posters distributed at conferences	3,5
Number of printer copies & online downloads of flyers & policy briefs	3000

4.1.2 Joint EDEN and FIDELIS Website

After the joint Kick-Off meeting of EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS projects, it was agreed that the sister projects should have a joint website, making the platform a “one-stop-shop” for all the latest news and updates related to digital repositories preservation and curation in Europe. The joint website went live on 31st March 2025 at the url www.eden-fidelis.eu and it is planned and structured to ensure visibility for all the EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS assets, namely the tools and services of the projects, spreading the awareness of EOSC sustainability through the TDRs and archives. The website also provides access to clear and concise information on the future actions and achieved goals of the project.

The content structure for the website will combine relevant information for both projects, including project overviews, our networks, frameworks & models developed through the projects, open calls for repositories support, training area with necessary resources for TDRs and trustworthy archives, as well as area on most up-to-date events and news. The agreed information infrastructure can be found

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below, with the areas released in the first website version marked blue, and those in yellow to be launched at a later iteration of the website.

Figure 3 EOSC EDEN - FIDELIS Website Information architecture

Different iterations of the website will be implemented throughout the course of the projects, showcasing the development of project’s main objectives and milestones. The website will be monitored for smooth UX experience, to ensure optimised levels of engagement and the best usable format of the project outputs. Currently, the website provides an overview of both projects, and early news about project progress, such as FIDELIS Network Launch or TTRAM Model overview, as well as other relevant project updates, such as events, where the community can be part of.

Figure 4 EOSC EDEN FIDELIS homepage mock-up

4.1.3 Editorial plan: joining efforts with EDEN

Alongside the joint website, EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS projects will closely collaborate on their communication and dissemination efforts. The FIDELIS 36-month awareness campaign, and TDR Network expansion and promotion will be implemented throughout a series of multimedia, including social media posts, newsletters, publications, webinars, videos, TDR stories, and illustrations. Since the current landscape involves a variety of digital repositories, with diverse levels of maturity, domains or services offered, our multimedia is tailored to showcase each of their interests and entice the audience to consider becoming a part of the TDR network. Through bi-weekly meetings with the EOSC EDEN communications team, we aim to revise and update the editorial content with most relevant news, events and opportunities for our stakeholders, while avoiding “audience fatigue” from the two sister projects.

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Post Topic	Post type	FIDELIS Campaign Type	Project	Lead	Status	Publish Date	Link to post example	LinkedIn Post	X/ Bluesky Post	Newsletter	Notes
2	Introduction Post	Campaign 1 Awareness	FIDELIS		Published	23/01/2025	https://www.linkedin.com/fe	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
3	All-consortium Webinar	Campaign 1 Awareness	FIDELIS		Published	23/01/2025	https://www.linkedin.com/fe	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
4	FIDELIS KOM Day 1 Wrap Up	Campaign 1 Awareness	FIDELIS		Published	04/02/2025	https://www.linkedin.com/fe	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
5	FIDELIS - EDEN joint sessions	Some post	Joint		Published	04/02/2025	https://www.linkedin.com/fe	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
6	FIDELIS Day 2 Wrap Up	Some post	Joint		Published	05/02/2025	https://www.linkedin.com/fe	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
7	EOOSC Association project announcement	News-piece	Joint		Published	07/02/2025	https://www.linkedin.com/fe	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
8	FIDELIS advances digital preservation	Campaign 1 Awareness	FIDELIS		Published	10/02/2025	https://www.linkedin.com/fe	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
9	FAIRFEST Re-share	Campaign 1 Awareness	FIDELIS		Published	25/02/2025	https://www.linkedin.com/fe	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
10	Video Pill from Partners (Maaike)		FIDELIS		Published	18/03/2025	https://www.linkedin.com/oo	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
11	Open Science 101 and priorities		FIDELIS		In process	21/03/2025		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
12	Website is Live Announcement	Some post	Joint		In process			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
13	FIDELIS Introductory Video	Campaign 1 Awareness	FIDELIS		Not Started			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
14	Video Pill from Partners (Damien)	Campaign 1 Awareness	FIDELIS		In process	24/03/2025		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
15	RDA 24th Plenary Promotion					26/03/2025		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
16	EOOSC EDEN and FIDELIS in EOOSC Landsc					28/03/2025		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
17	Video Pill from Partners (Jan)	Campaign 1 Awareness	FIDELIS		In process	01/04/2025		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
18	Video Pill from Partners (Mar)	Campaign 1 Awareness	FIDELIS		In process	03/04/2025		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
19	FAIR FRIDAY - A brief history of FAIR Prin		FIDELIS		Not Started	04/04/2025		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
20	FAIR FRIDAY - EOOSC Overview		FIDELIS		Not Started			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
21	TDR in the Spotlight Series		FIDELIS		Not Started			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		

Figure 5 FIDELIS editorial plan management file

While social media, publications, newsletter, press releases will be coordinated with EOOSC EDEN (sections 5.4 to 5.7), unique communication outputs by FIDELIS will involve videos, TDR stories and illustrations. Over the course of the project, we will release one professional, custom-designed video to raise awareness about the importance of a shared compliance framework for repositories across disciplines and institutes. Additional 10 video interviews will be released throughout the duration of the project, displaying the benefits of the TDR support programmes.

Alongside the videos, stakeholders will be able to interact with 6 downloadable TDR stories, which will be designed and produced with the repositories engaged in the Network, with the aim of showcasing the added value of TDR Network membership.

During M3 and M4, the FIDELIS communication team initiated the introductory promotion of FIDELIS' main assets, including the FIDELIS Network launch led by Pillar 2, harmonisation efforts led by Pillar 3, and mapping of digital repositories landscape led by Pillar 4.

In a collaborative effort, we launched the FIDELIS Network on April 16th, 2025. The promotion of the Network comprised of several activities, including:

- [the “Our Networks” section launch on the joint website,](#)
- [publication of the news piece on the FIDELIS Network launch,](#) accessible via website and social media channels,
- [publication of the news on the EOOSC Forum,](#)
- and outreach to early-adopter repositories with a personal invitation email to join.

Figure 6 FIDELIS LinkedIn posts promoting main assets

To provide the digital repositories an overview of the FIDELIS Network vision and planned activities, the FIDELIS consortium will also host an introductory webinar⁹ on May 13th, 2025.

The communication activities will also be enriched with the design and publication of digital visual representations of workflows, technical challenges and relationships among different user types, often showcased in the form of infographics. Such infographics can be utilised and replicated during presentations, events, or training sessions.

4.1.4 Social Media

To garner an active and diverse open science community, FIDELIS leverages a range of channels to reach a variety of audiences on social media and convert those members into engaged stakeholders. While the website will be a joint endeavour with EOSC EDEN, FIDELIS will keep its own distinct online presence. Since the launch of the project, FIDELIS began building its community through a variety of social media platforms, notably: LinkedIn, BlueSky, and YouTube. Through tailored content and consistent interaction, FIDELIS engages the representatives of various trustworthy digital repositories and thereby raising the project’s awareness and opportunities provided by the FIDELIS initiatives.

As of April 2025, FIDELIS has 255 followers on social media. Through a continuous reach out to the community and consistent publication, the project increases the interest and trust in its content, which is confirmed by the rise of unique visitors, page views and user engagement collected by the in-built analytics tools.

⁹ <https://eden-fidelis.eu/events/fidelis-network-launch-introductory-webinar>

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Table 3 FIDELIS Social media accounts

Social Media	Link
BlueSky	@fidelis-project.bsky.social
LinkedIn	FIDELIS
YouTube	FIDELIS Project YouTube Channel

We will continue to implement the communication activities through various social media channels and the joint website. Particular attention will be given to showcase project participation in internal and external events, open calls, available training, highlight of successful digital repositories, and project achievements, all to amplify project efforts and to consolidate an engaged online community.

Table 4 Social media KPIs

Social Media	Measure	KPI
Social Media Channels	Followers across all platforms	3000 – M12 5000 – M36

BlueSky

To be continuously aware of the needs and interests of the European research community, and as a newly started project, FIDELIS team opted for the use of BlueSky over X, given the deterioration of the platform's regulation and growing expenses for account maintenance. Like X's micro-blogging, BlueSky allows users to share concise messages and reach out to interest-specific audiences. The platform is designed for communicating concise immediate updates. FIDELIS will leverage Blue Sky for live event updates and raising awareness about the opportunities and training for the digital repositories and their research communities.

To achieve its benchmarks and target a wider audience, FIDELIS will incorporate the relevant hashtags provided in the table below. This allows to expand the community and spread awareness about digital repositories and their network expansion across the social media platform.

Table 5 FIDELIS Relevant hashtags

Category	Digital Repositories	Research & Infrastructures	Policy Makers
Hashtags	#OpenScience #FAIRrepositories #TrustworthyRepositories #DataManagementNews #RepositoriesOpportunities #digitalpreservation	#EOSC #FAIRData #OpenData #ResearchEurope #EOSCProjects #OpenAccess	#DataPolicy #SciencePolicy #EUScience #DataGovernance #ResearchEthics #HorizonEurope

LinkedIn

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As one of the cornerstone platforms for professional developments and networking, LinkedIn also enables users to connect and spread awareness on topics relevant to their work and interests. By publishing relevant and diverse content on LinkedIn, FIDELIS has already started building an active online community of stakeholders and aims at satisfying the need of quality content that helps address the need for a better interconnected digital repositories community.

Figure 7 FIDELIS LinkedIn posts

Figure 8 FIDELIS LinkedIn analytics (extract) from KOM to end of April 2025

YouTube

As video content is fundamental for communicating the benefits of a European digital repositories network, FIDELIS will produce and publish several videos on YouTube, a major platform for video sharing. The goal is creating and disseminating videos and interviews that spread knowledge and awareness about the digital repositories and the importance of trustworthiness for them.

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The published videos on YouTube will be subsequently disseminated on other social media and/or embedded on the joint website to increase their visibility.

Figure 9 Embedded YouTube video on FIDELIS - EOSC EDEN website

4.1.5 Newsletters

One newsletter will be issued every three months, its content shaped around the milestone results of the work planning, featuring TDR related news and events published on EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS website. The newsletter will also be conducted with EOSC EDEN, avoiding “audience fatigue”, and ensuring all relevant information is effectively shared with our shared stakeholders. The first issue of the newsletter will be shared with 55 subscribers on April 30th, 2025.

Aside from collecting newsletter subscribers through events, face-to-face meetings, consortium network and social media, we have also set up a sign-up section for newsletter through the website. This way, we can harness a valued network database interested in receiving updates about the project. The collection of these contacts complies with the GDPR and the EOSC EDEN FIDELIS Privacy Policy.

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Figure 10 FIDELIS - EOSC EDEN Newsletter subscription page

4.1.6 Press Releases

Press releases will be produced and distributed to media partners any time the project will need to share content that’s newsworthy and relevant to project development. The first press release about the outcomes of the joint kick-off meeting in Helsinki, Finland, held February 4th to February 6th, was published in M1, while the second press release will be published in M18 of the project.

The first press release was distributed across partners’ websites, which engage a significant number of digital repositories and research communities.

4.1.7 Dissemination of Research Outputs

The dissemination of the project research outputs will be done via different resources.

OA Repositories. According to the FIDELIS DMP plan, all public documents and reports as well as data and software will also be published on ZENODO, the general-purpose repository for multidisciplinary research results, that will allow FIDELIS to analyse number of views, citations and downloads per each publication. GitHub will also be exploited for software and linked to ZENODO for preservation and DOI creation.

EOSC collaboration platforms. The channels run by the EOSC Association will also be exploited, starting from the EOSC Forum that FIDELIS comms team has already joined and the EOSC HE Communications monthly meetings that the comms team is already attending.

Open peer-review scientific journals and collections. When not published at ORE, FIDELIS will consider publishing scientific papers in other platforms, such as CODATA Data Science Journal, Patterns and International Journal of Digital Curation, Research Ideas and Outcomes Journal, DaMaLOS (Metadata and Research (objects) Management for Linked Open Science) journal, FAIR

Connect Journal, amongst others. The aim is to further disseminate FIDELIS work in terms of FAIR and data repositories interoperability, to a wider audience.

Open Research Europe. Open Research Europe is an open access publishing venue for European Commission-funded researchers across all disciplines, with no author fees. FIDELIS partners will also consider if to publish via this platform.

Horizon Results Platform. Finally, a Key Exploitable Result template for each relevant output will be filled and shared via the EC Horizon Results Platform portal, making project results more visible to the European audience, as well as assisting FIDELIS in defining sustainability and exploitation opportunities for the results.

Table 6 FIDELIS Research outputs dissemination

Dissemination of project & research results	Measure	KPI
Publications	avg. downloads per individual resource (via Zenodo)	300
Publications	number of articles published in Open Access and peer-review magazines and journals, inc. Open Research Europe	3

4.2 Campaign #2: TDR Network expansion

The purpose of this campaign is to facilitate network expansion and repository improvement by promoting FIDELIS outcomes, the training and mentoring programmes activities. The set of activities envisaged as part of this campaign targets mainly *SG1 European digital repositories at different levels of capability and maturity, SG2 Research infrastructures, SG3 Certification bodies and SG5 Service providers, suppliers of data repository technology.*

FIDELIS offers three main “routes” for supporting and upskilling repositories, with the goal to foster their integration into the Network and enable peer-to-peer support:

- **A. A “cascading grant” mechanism ‘Support for the adoption of solutions’** to be used to select, through open calls and an inclusive evaluation process, repositories from multiple disciplines and geographical areas to provide them with the financial means and guidance to implement and adopt good practices, tools and services increasing their trustworthiness. Two cycles of support programmes will be run in the framework of Pillar 4 for expanding the TDR Network, enhancing repository trustworthiness by guiding them on the use of services, tools, methodologies and policies.
- **B. A series of openly available training interventions** which will run throughout the project lifetime. Open training interventions will have two strands: a more technical one for repository developers and one related to repository governance and management aspects.

- **C. A mentoring programme** for peer-to-peer hands-on support to align with the standards and requirements of the Transparent Trustworthy Repository Attributes Matrix that will be designed by the project, bridging gaps between less and more advanced repositories.

Pillar 5 will put in place mechanisms to i) **ensure visibility and promotion** to all the above listed activities, ii) **support the management of online activities** during the different phases, from the publication of the open calls on the FIDELIS website and Grants Platform, up to to user support for their application as well as to evaluators for the entire evaluation process (see section on the FIDELIS Grants Platform), iii) and ultimately to provide visibility to the onboarded TDRs and the outcomes of all the three support mechanisms.

In particular, the following actions have been envisaged:

Online webinars: Presentation of results from WP5, WP6 and WP7 to the community for discussion and to collect feedback. Pillar 5 will support in the organisation and promotion of these webinars, publishing online pages on the public website, collecting registrations and including them in the editorial plan. Live support will also be provided in running the webinars, chairing them and doing live SoMe streaming.

Surveys & Consultations: Online surveys, consultation activities on business model and governance and organisational mechanisms for the federation, community needs, technical implementation, future expectation. Pillar 5 will support the publication of the surveys on the FIDELIS website and their promotion across all relevant channels. Support for processing of the results can also be provided, as well as public evidence of the outcomes and highlights in the form of news pieces and articles, collaboratively written with the partners responsible for surveys.

TDR online Forum: A TDR forum area established as the online home for the Network secretariat activities and day by day interaction with the engaged Repositories. More details are provided in section 4.2.1.

Table 7 FIDELIS TDR Network expansion - dissemination

Dissemination of project & research results	Measure	KPI
Online webinars	No of webinar participants	Low 30 – high 80
Surveys and consultations	No of consulted community members	Low 50 – high 100
TDR Forum	No of individuals signed up to the Forum	100

4.2.1 TDR Online Forum

By M16 a TDR Forum area will be implemented as digital space for the repositories to interact among themselves, share best practices and debate about everyday operations. The area should be online and different while linked to the public website. During the FIDELIS Kick-off meeting the consortium

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brainstormed on which functionalities the consortium would like to see there. The following were noted:

- Discussion boards
- Link to reference docs/guidelines
- working groups to discuss topics such as best practices, recommendations, guidelines, and others
- Jobs board
- newsletter/ digests
- address book/experts list / Contact list of relevant experts on certain topics and/or mentors
- Coordinate sustainability efforts
- Training materials
- A Nextcloud-like environment coupled with a discussion board. Free (Libre) software.
- Open forum / public posts to ask questions (like Quora)
- Dissemination, quick polling, asking input/feedback from peers
- Glossary
- Different spaces for different themes.
- The possibility to share documents
- Events calendar
- Integrated online meeting possibilities
- tags or labels to be able to narrow down to specific communities

A deeper requirement and specification gathering session will be run to investigate the functionalities of the FORUM and the expectations from FIDELIS WPs for exploiting it for their tasks. Some first inputs were not collected during the landscape survey launched in April 2025.

The possibility to not introduce a new tool but to rely on the EOSC-Association channels, such as the existing EOSC Forum, will also be considered, taking into consideration the pros and cons of extending it to entities which are not EOSC Association members neither linked to Horizon Europe projects.

4.2.2 FIDELIS Grants Platform

The communication and technical management of the open calls will be performed via the FIDELIS Financial Support Platform, a tailor-made adaption of the TRUST-GRANTS™ platform. It will be developed to perform an open, transparent and process of application for funding and in-kind support, namely the open calls that the project will launch over the 36 months.

With a user-friendly interface and navigation functionalities, the dashboard is easily accessed through creation of an account on eden-fidelis.eu and serves the different phases necessary for a streamlined submission process for both applicants and for administrators.

ID	Call	Title	User	Organisation	Organisation Type	Creation date	Submission date	Workflow	Evaluated	Action
MACHINE_READABLE-153	6f Availability and machine readability of data policies with FAIRsharing			DCC	Service providers	30/01/2024 - 15:57 CET	30/01/2024 - 15:57 CET	Withdrawn	Yes	
MACHINE_READABLE-156	6f Availability and machine readability of data policies with FAIRsharing			DCC	Service providers	30/01/2024 - 16:25 CET		Draft	Yes	
MACHINE_READABLE-160	6f Availability and machine readability of data policies with FAIRsharing			Consortium of universities of Catalonia (CSUC)	Research Communities & Infrastructures	06/02/2024 - 08:28 CET	06/02/2024 - 08:28 CET	Withdrawn	Yes	
MACHINE_READABLE-192	6f Availability and machine readability of data policies with FAIRsharing			TU/e	Research Performing Organisations	15/03/2024 - 17:08 CET	15/03/2024 - 17:08 CET	In Evaluation	Yes	
MACHINE_READABLE-215	6f Availability and machine readability of data policies with FAIRsharing			Digital Repository of Ireland	Service providers	26/03/2024 - 11:59 CET	28/03/2024 - 15:56 CET	In Evaluation	Yes	
MACHINE_READABLE-218	6f Availability and machine readability of data policies with FAIRsharing			University of Sheffield, UK / UK Reproducibility Network	National Level Initiatives	26/03/2024 - 13:29 CET	27/03/2024 - 19:55 CET	In Evaluation	Yes	
MACHINE_READABLE-249	6f Availability and machine readability of data policies with FAIRsharing			Iscte - University Institute of Lisbon	Research Performing Organisations	30/03/2024 - 19:05 CET	30/03/2024 - 21:41 CET	In Evaluation	Yes	
MACHINE_READABLE-250	6f Availability and machine readability of data policies with FAIRsharing			ACC CYFRONET AGH	Research Performing Organisations	30/03/2024 - 22:29 CET	30/03/2024 - 22:30 CET	In Evaluation	Yes	
MACHINE_READABLE-251	6f Availability and machine readability of data policies with FAIRsharing			CNUJUST	National Level Initiatives	30/03/2024 - 23:10 CET	31/03/2024 - 13:23 CET	In Evaluation	Yes	
MACHINE_READABLE-256	6f Availability and machine readability of data policies with FAIRsharing			IMISE University of Leipzig	National Level Initiatives	31/03/2024 - 20:15 CET	31/03/2024 - 23:55 CET	In Evaluation	Yes	

Figure 11 Preview of the Grant platform interface

Applications & Evaluation of Proposals. Once FIDELIS open calls are launched, the platform becomes the principal interface for the applications received. By accessing their own profile, the evaluators can visualise the applications they have been assigned (but not the concurrent ones assigned to other reviewers), and perform their evaluation. A comments option is available on the voting system, allowing evaluators to record the reasons for their evaluations for other evaluators to see. After the closure of each call, a ranking of the applications helps determine which one has been approved for financial and/or in-kind support. Applicants can track the status of their application directly from their dashboard. Moreover, instant message functionality allows direct contact with the administrators.

Figure 12 Open Call standard evaluation workflow

Still to be finalised with the remit of Pillar 4, the evaluation workflow will be performed entirely via the FIDELIS Financial Support Platform with the allocation of evaluators from a designated pool of project partners to each eligible proposal.

The platform will continue to be used during the implementation phase as the primary environment for assessment and monitoring of the funded project’ results and to communicate between the project and the successful applicants.

Administration & Funding Requests & Reports. Thanks to the Grants Platform, all the profiles are stored and managed in one single place, allowing the tracking of the information in each single phase of the Open Call workflow. The platform enables easy management of the status of the applications (e.g., eligible, under evaluation, approved, monitored) and the subsequent funding steps are also described.

All open calls will be published via the FIDELIS website and disseminated widely. The outcome of the calls will be published via the FIDELIS website within 30 days of the evaluations being carried out and will include a description of supported applicants, the date of the award, the duration, and the organisation and country of the successful applicants.

4.3 Campaign #3 TDR Network promotion and visibility

The purpose of the activities listed within this campaign is to ensure that the FIDELIS network, its members and its working practices are visible, renowned and presented to the EOSC community. Position the Network as the voice of the TDR community.

Visibility to the TDR network will be provided via:

- **Videos:** the creation of **one professional, custom-designed video** to raise awareness about the importance of a shared compliance framework for repositories across disciplines and institutes. Additional **video interviews** with the beneficiaries of the TDR support programme will also be filmed at events and meetings, with FIDELIS and EDEN partners and experts as well as by interviewing stakeholders and repository representatives, beneficiaries or not of the FIDELIS grants.
- **TDR stories:** Downloadable TDR stories designed and produced with the repositories engaged in the Network with the aim to showcase the value add for joining and stimulate replication. The stories will be designed as downloadable factsheets available in the FIDELIS Zenodo community. TDR will be collected from the repositories that benefited from FIDELIS training programmes, as well as other repositories that are part of FIDELIS network and have high levels of data FAIRness.
- **Illustrations:** Online visual representations of workflows, technical challenges, relationships among different user types across a repository life cycle, best practices, etc. in the form of infographics. Visuals will be realized in collaboration with partners working in the definition of the mechanisms and procedures for the TDR network.

Table 8 FIDELIS TDR Network promotion and visibility - dissemination

Dissemination of project & research results	Measure	KPI
Videos	No. of views per video.	300
TDR stories	No of stories released and disseminated.	20
Illustrations	No of illustrations designed, published on the website and disseminated via presentations, events, training activities.	10

4.4 Campaign #4 Strategic Alliances Trust-IT / CSC

To ensure the mechanisms put in place, lessons learnt, and results of the FIDELIS project are continuously shared and assessed with the EOSC community at large, three online workshops will be organised with EOSC landscape projects, data – infrastructures and international initiatives not supported by FIDELIS support programme and not engaged in the TDR Network creation. The

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workshops will be targeting in particular the EOSC-related actors and the EOSC related projects and those initiatives with which FIDELIS will establish strategic partnerships and agreements. Each of the workshops will be dedicated to assessing some of the specific topics related to adoption of FAIR data practices by repositories, without losing the EOSC perspective.

Bilateral working online meetings will be organised as well, with selected representatives of the abovementioned initiatives, to collect further advice and exchange on specific aspects relevant for consolidating the Network (e.g. legal, IP, privacy, operations, governance models, amongst others).

Table 9 Strategic Alliances - dissemination

Dissemination of project & research results	Measure	KPI
Strategic Alliance Workshops	No. of participants to each workshop.	low=50 high=90
Bilateral meetings	No of meetings organised	8

5 Events

5.1 FIDELIS events

In order to facilitate collaboration and strengthen the network of digital repositories in Europe, a series of targeted events will be organised in the course of the project with clear objectives, FIDELIS audiences, and with expected outputs in mind. Each event will have dedicated support before the event for its organisation (agenda set-up, selection of speakers, clear registration procedure accessible via event web pages). Ahead of the event, the event will be promoted across target stakeholders (ensuring social media visibility and direct email marketing). During the event, the FIDELIS team will support the facilitation of the event and engage in live social media posting. Lastly, after the event we will ensure coordination and distribution of post-event reporting, and publication of any promotional event takeaways and other materials.

The organisation of various FIDELIS events will depend on the needs of the different project work packages (WPs) and shared with the EOSC EDEN consortium. These events will support WPs in delivering their results. FIDELIS communication team will prepare customised branding for each series of events, thus enhancing the visibility of the project and distinct visual identity.

The organisation of these events may be organised as stand-alone events by FIDELIS or also combined, when appropriate with events organised by other initiatives to maximise effort and impact.

Specifically for engagement and training purposes with regards to the repository community, several online and face-to-face workshops will be organised. Furthermore, FIDELIS will contribute to three Bootcamps to be organised by the EOSC EDEN project, with the goal of discussing, presenting, testing

and adopting solutions developed in the EOSC EDEN project by repositories, archives and registries, in collaboration with FIDELIS.

Collaboration with other projects will be considered depending on the project’s needs and aspirations for supporting the repository community.

5.2 Bilateral working meetings

As part of the effort to disseminate the lessons learned and results of the FIDELIS project, we will organise bilateral working meetings, held online. These meetings with selected representatives of the EOSC-related projects, data infrastructures will be asked for contribution and knowledge exchange on specific aspects relevant for consolidating the TDR Network. Some topics to be covered concern legal matters, IP, privacy, and potential operations and governance models.

5.3 Webinars

The organisation of webinars will be used for the presentation of results from WP5, WP6 and WP7 to the repositories community for discussion and further feedback collection.

Table 10 Webinars organised during the FIDELIS project

Webinar Schedule	WP Relevance	Theme	KPI - no. of attendees
M4	WP5	Overview of the Trustworthy Repositories Attributes Matrix (TTRAM)	Low 30 - high 80
M8	WP5	Interoperability and Harmonisation Across Repositories: Challenges and Solutions	Low 30 - high 80
M16	WP6	Introduction to TDR Forum: How Digital Repositories Can Continue to Thrive	Low 30 - high 80
M20	WP6	Technical and Legal Aspects of Repository Federation in EOSC	Low 30 - high 80
M28	WP7	Upskilling and Supporting Repositories: Training, Mentoring, and Financial Incentives	Low 30 - high 80
M32	WP7	The Future of Trustworthy Repositories: Strategic Roadmap and Community Engagement	Low 30 - high 80

5.4 Final Conference

The FIDELIS Final Conference and graduation ceremony will bring together all the repositories supported and trained during the project. During this hybrid event, we will have an opportunity to showcase FIDELIS exploitable results and publicly award the repositories that joined the Network. The event will be organised in the last months of FIDELIS. The event will be co-located with EOSC EDEN final conference and possibly combined with another key event in Europe (EOSC Symposium, IDCC, or others)

5.5 Third-party events

FIDELIS partners will actively participate in relevant third-party events as speakers or presenters, organising sessions or workshops, or deliver presentations. By attending and participating at third party events, we are able to:

- Promote of the FIDELIS work to different target stakeholders.
- Collect new contacts for database enrichment opportunities
- Engage directly with potential FIDELIS audiences
- Identify different synergies for potential collaboration and knowledge transfer
- Disseminate the results related to TDRs and engage the open science community.

Table 11 Upcoming Third-party events until M12, to be extended further

Event	Location	Audience
RDA 24th Plenary Meeting	Virtual	Repository managers, data stewards, researchers
50th Annual Conference of IASSIST	Bristol, UK	Repository managers, data stewards
DARIAH Annual Event	Gottingen, Germany	Open science experts, digital preservation managers
Open Science Fair	Cern, Switzerland	open science experts, researchers
EOSC Symposium 2025	Berlin, Germany	repository managers, researchers, e-infrastructures, data stewards

6 Monitoring and Assessment

Evaluation of the Communication and Marketing activities will be based on several points. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are tracked monthly: monitoring the dissemination, communication, papers submission and presence/organisation at events. Five monitoring trackers have been built based on the reporting forms available on the EC funding and tenders portal entry point for participants in funded projects. By using them as a benchmark, it will smooth the reporting process

and ensure that the communication and dissemination activities are properly reported. Instructions about how to track the activities have already been shared with FIDELIS partners.

Table 12 FIDELIS list of Monitoring and Assessment trackers

Tracker	Description
Publications	Papers, articles and other publications published by FAIR-IMPACT consortium partners
Dissemination Activities	Performed activities to reach target audiences, that is, any potential user of the project results. These activities can be: Clustering Activities, Collaboration with EU-funded projects, Conference, Education and Training Events, Meetings, Other Scientific Collaboration, Other Scientific Cooperation, Other
Communication Activities	Performed activities to reach a wide audience, that is, not just aimed to reach potential end-users, but the general audience, including media and general public. The aim is to promote the project in general and its value-added and not just the project results. Examples of some communication activities are visual identity (e.g. logo), public website, flyers, social media, videos, press releases, etc.
Events	Events organised under FIDELIS and also all third-party events (events not organised by FIDELIS) where FIDELIS had visibility (e.g. poster, exhibition stand, lightning talk, panel discussion, presentation, paper submission etc.)
KPIs	General KPIs related to communication and dissemination activities

An online visual Dashboard will also be set up to measure the online presence and the community engagement in real-time, as well as allow users to visualise trends and compare overtime performance of FIDELIS website and social media channels.

7 Conclusions and next steps

This document describes the “Communication & dissemination strategy & plan” of FIDELIS, as part of “WP11 - Strategic alliance, cascading grants, communication and dissemination - phase 1” and it paves the way to the future set of activities to be set and executed in the upcoming months, keeping a bright vision of the KPIs in order to monitor the results and achievements reached.

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As outlined in this deliverable, several dissemination and communication activities will be put in place to engage with each one of the stakeholder groups, to ensure the overall goals of FIDELIS will be achieved. This will be a joint effort with all FIDELIS partners with effort within this work package, with a close liaison with the other partners to ensure their work is properly supported by the FIDELIS communication and dissemination team.

In the first 12 months of the project, the communication team aims to create a strong online presence (e.g. 3000 social media followers), support the dissemination by providing the project team members attending the third-party events listed above with branded materials and online visibility (e.g. social media posts, post-event articles) stressing the key messages from FIDELIS perspective and support the newly launched FIDELIS Network to reach out to the target stakeholders to engage them in the further development of the FIDELIS Network and the TTRAM Matrix (e.g. a community consultation on the network business model and governance, TTRAM workshop, public webinars), and identify the main needs from repositories for its training programme. The project will leverage on the multiplier effect of the digital repositories onboarded to the Network for efficient communication.

During the 2nd year of the project, the communication and dissemination efforts will start on promoting the training course provided and the first impact results they are bringing to repositories and their own communities. Looking at the network, promotion efforts will be focused supporting its growth through the organisation of online workshops that will increase the Network members' understanding of common legal issues and requirements facing TDRs

8 Annex 1 List of digital repositories onboarded to the Network at the beginning of the project

Domain	Repository name	Repository owner	Country	Onboarding partner
Social Sciences & Humanities	Finnish Social Science Data Archive	Tampere University / FSD	FI	CESSDA ERIC / TAU-FSD
	UK Data Service	UK Data Archive / University of Essex	UK	CESSDA ERIC /UKDS-UESSEXS
	Slovak Archive of Social Data	Slovak Academy of Science	SK	CESSDA ERIC
	Croatian Social Sciences Archive	University of Zagreb	CR	CESSDA ERIC
	The Language Bank of Finland	Finnish Universities, Ministry of Research & Education	FI	CSC
	The Tromsø Repository of Language and Linguistics	The Arctic University of Norway (UIT)	NO	UIT
	SIKT Research Data Archive Service	SIKT	NO	SIKT
	GESIS Data Service	Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences	DE	GESIS
	DANS Data Stations and Vault	Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS)	NL	KNAW-DANS
	LINDAT/CLARIA-CZ	Charles University of Prague	CZ	CLARIN/CU
CLARIN-PL	Wroclaw University of Technology	PL	CLARIN/CU	
Biomedical Sciences	UniProt	UniProt Consortium (EMBL-EBI, SIB and PIR)	DE	ELIXIR

Domain	Repository name	Repository owner	Country	Onboarding partner
	MetaboLights	EBI	UK	ELIXIR
	Genome Wide Association Study Catalog (GWAS Catalog)	EBI	UK	ELIXIR
	STRING	Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics	CH	SIB
	Cellosaurus	Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics	CH	SIB
	GNPIS	INRAE / URGI research unit	FR	INRAE
Agri-food	Agroportal	INRAE	FR	INRAE
	RIVeC - Repository of the Institute for Vegetable Crops	Institute for Vegetable Crops Smederevska Palanka	RS	UoB
	FiVeR - Repository of the Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops	Repository of the Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops, Novi Sad	RS	UoB
Environmental Sciences	World Data Center for Climate	DKRZ	DE	DKRZ
	GFZ Data Services	GFZ German Research Centre for Geosciences	DE	DKRZ
	PANGEA Data Publisher	University of Bremen	DE	UniBH
	EasyData	INRAE and other RPO / Data Terra research infrastructure	FR	INRAE
	UTM (Unidad Tecnologia Marina)	CSIC	ES	CSIC
	IGME (Instituto Geologico y Minero de España)	CSIC	ES	CSIC
	SOCIB Data Catalog	CSIC	ES	CSIC

Domain	Repository name	Repository owner	Country	Onboarding partner
Physical & Material Sciences	ESRF Data Portal	ESRF	FR	ESRF
	CER – Central Repository of the Institute of Technology and Metallurgy	Institute of Technology and Metallurgy, University of Belgrade	RS	UoB
Generic	Fairdata	CSC	FI	CSC
	RechercheDataGouv	French Ministry of Education & Research	FR	INRAE/MESR
	DataverseNO	UIT	NO	UIT
	Edmond	Max Planck Society	DE	DKRZ
	RADAR	FIZ Karlsruhe GmbH	DE	DKRZ
	ZFDM	Center for Sustainable Research Data Management, University Hamburg	DE	DKRZ
	DAIS – Digital Archive of SASA	Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts, Belgrade	RS	UoB